

Direct Immunofluorescence of Renal Biopsy and Its Clinicopathological Correlation

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Abstract:

Aim & Objectives: This study was undertaken to analyze the strength of Direct Immunofluorescence microscopy in the diagnosis of renal disease presented with various clinical symptoms and compare the findings with similar studies published. The purpose of our study is to assess the histopathological spectrum of renal biopsies conjoining with The Direct Immunofluorescence in our population. We studied 105 consecutive renal biopsies over a period of 11 months. The Histopathological and Direct Immunofluorescence findings were carefully documented and analyzed. The morphology was then correlated with clinical features, in relation to the age and gender of the patient.

Results: In our patient population, primary glomerulonephritis mainly focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS) was the most common prevalent kidney disease. Nephrotic syndrome (NS) was the leading indication for renal biopsy, followed by acute renal failure. Maximum Direct Immunofluorescence positivity was seen in Lupus Nephritis (6/6 cases showed FULL-HOUSE effect (Positive for IgG, IgM, IgA, Complement C3, C1Q, Kappa & Lambda).

Conclusion: Direct Immunofluorescence assisted to correct diagnosis of renal disease in parallel with light microscopic examination along its correlation with clinical features and serological parameters. In less than 5% of patients, electron microscopy might be essential.

Keywords: Direct Immunofluorescence, Glomerulonephritis, Nephropathy.

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Introduction

Direct Immunofluorescence (DIF) serves as a potent auxiliary technique for the thorough pathological assessment of renal biopsies, aiding in the differential diagnosis of glomerulonephritis. It is employed in conjunction with Histopathological examination and Electron microscopy to accurately diagnose renal diseases. This study aims to present the spectrum of renal conditions observed over 11months period and the practical challenges a practicing nephropathologist may encounter while using the DIF technique, which is available in only a few centres in India.

Materials and Methodology

A total of 105 consecutive renal biopsies were analysed. For each patient, two cores of renal biopsies were obtained via percutaneous needle biopsy. The first core was fixed in 10% formalin,

embedded in paraffin and routinely stained with haematoxylin and eosin, periodic acid-schiff (PAS) stain and Jones stain for light microscopic examination. The second core, intended for direct immuno-fluorescence microscopy (DIFM) was immediately frozen and embedded in OCT (optimal cutting temperature) compound. Using FITC conjugated antisera against human IgG, IgA, IgM, C3, and fibrinogen, the standard DIF was performed. The staining patterns, including glomerular and extra glomerular locations, intensity and distribution (focal or diffuse, segmental or global) were meticulously observed, recorded and reported. Glomerular staining was categorized as mesangial or capillary wall (or both), while capillary wall staining was described as granular or linear. The histopathology and DIF slides were independently reviewed by two pathologists, and

their findings were later compared to arrive at a final diagnosis. Clinical information from nephrologists' data submissions was also considered alongside the biopsy results.

Results

Within 11 months period, a total of 105 renal biopsies were received in the immunopathology department at Parul Sevashram hospital. Among these, In 9 cases, the renal biopsies were inadequate for routine light or direct immuno-fluorescence (DIF) microscopic analysis. Specifically, 6 cases were nonrepresentative and in the remaining 3 cases, no glomeruli were visible—only medullary tissue was included. Consequently, the final analysis focused on the remaining 96 biopsies. Out of these cases, 45 were male and 51 were female. (Table 1)

In our patient population, primary glomerulonephritis merged as the most prevalent kidney disease, accounting for 56 (58.33%) of all cases. Among primary GN cases, focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS) was the most common subtype, representing 23.2% (13/56) of primary glomerulonephritis, followed by membranous glomerulopathy at 17.9% (10/56). Most primary GN diagnoses occurred during the sixth decade of life as indicated in table 2. Nephrotic syndrome (NS) was the leading indication for renal biopsy, followed by acute renal failure. Clinical syndromes associated with each histologic category are detailed in table 3.

Direct immunofluorescence (DIF) examination was performed for all 96 cases. In focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS), IgA alone was the most common immunoreactant observed in 30.7% (4/13) of cases along with kappa and lambda chain positivity in tubular cast.

All cases of membranous nephropathy (10/10) showed positivity for IgG, complement C3, kappa and lambda chains. Type 1 membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis (1/1) showed whole panel positivity.

IgA nephropathy constituted 7.3% (7/96) of all renal biopsy diagnoses and 12.5% (7/56) of primary glomerular diseases. The most frequent presentation was hemato-proteinuria, followed by

nephritic syndrome. All cases of IgA nephropathy showed mesangial deposits of IgA and complement C3 deposits along with kappa and lambda chain positivity.

Out of a total of 4 cases of crescentic GN, 3 cases exhibited 2+ mesangial staining for IgG and complement C3. None of these cases showed IgM, IgA reactive mesangial deposits. 1 case did not show any positivity for IgG and complement C3 but kappa and lambda chains were positive in tubular cast. (Table 4)

Diabetic nephropathy emerged as the most common secondary glomerulonephritis (GN), accounting for 10.41% of all cases. Lupus nephritis followed at 7.3% and amyloidosis at 4.16%.

All (6/6) cases met the clinical, serological and immunopathological criteria for lupus nephritis. All were female patients. All patients tested positive for antinuclear antibodies (ANA). The most frequent clinical presentation included hemato-proteinuria in 4 cases, followed by specific clinical features of systemic lupus erythematosus in 2 cases. Notably, Class V was the predominant pathological subgroup. Full house staining for immunoglobulins was noted in all cases of lupus nephritis.

All (4/4) cases of amyloidosis showed positive immunofluorescence results for kappa light chains and negative immunofluorescence results for IgM, complement C3 and C1Q. 2/4 cases showed positive immunofluorescence results for lambda light chains.

Acute tubular injury was seen in 15.2% (15/96) of cases and tubulointerstitial nephritis (TIN) changes were observed in 3.1% (3/96) of cases.

1 out of 2 miscellaneous cause labelled as Monoclonal immune deposition disease showed bright staining of lambda chains in basement membranes of tubules, vessel walls and interstitium, weak staining in basement membrane of glomeruli with focal bright staining in the mesangium. Another miscellaneous cause labelled as Kappa restricted light chain deposition disease showed positive +3 mesangial deposits of kappa chains in tubular basement membrane and vessels.

Table 1: Distribution of all renal diseases observed in 96 native kidney biopsies over a period of 11 months

Major category	Renal diseases	Number of cases	Male to female ratio
Primary glomerulonephritis	Focal segmental glomerulosclerosis	13	7:6
	Membranous nephropathy	10	3:7
	Type I membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis	1	0:1
	IgA nephropathy	7	4:3

	Crescentic glomerulonephritis	4	1:3
	Diffuse proliferative glomerulonephritis	1	0:1
	Chronic glomerulosclerosis	9	4:5
	Mesangio proliferative glomerulonephritis	4	3:1
	Primary podocytopathy	7	1:6
Secondary glomerulonephritis	Lupus nephritis	6	0:6
	Amyloidosis	4	1:3
	Diabetic nephropathy	10	6:4
Tubulointerstitial nephritis	Acute tubulointerstitial nephritis	3	3:0
	Acute tubular injury	15	11:4
Miscellaneous	Monoclonal immune deposition disease	1	1:0
	Kappa restricted light chain deposition disease	1	0:1
	Total= 96		M:F= 45:51

Table 2: Distribution of renal diseases in different age groups

Renal Disease	<10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	>60	Total
Focal segmental glomerulosclerosis	-	-	3	3	1	3	3	13
Membranous nephropathy	-	-	2	2	4	2	-	10
Type I membranous proliferative glomerulonephritis	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
IgA nephropathy	-	1	4	2	-	-	-	7
Crescentic glomerulonephritis	-	1	-	-	1	1	1	4
Diffuse proliferative glomerulonephritis	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Chronic glomerulosclerosis	-	-	2	1	3	2	1	9
Mesangio proliferative glomerulonephritis	-	1	-	2	1	-	-	4
Primary podocytopathy	-	-	2	2	-	2	1	7
Lupus nephritis	-	1	3	-	2	-	-	6
Amyloidosis	-	-	1	-	1	1	1	4
Diabetic nephropathy	-	-	-	-	3	5	2	10
Acute tubulointerstitial nephritis	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	3
Acute tubular injury	-	1	2	4	2	3	3	15
Monoclonal immune deposition disease	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
Kappa restricted light chain deposition disease	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
	-	5	20	17	19	21	14	96

Table 3: Clinical presentation in various renal disease

Renal disease	Nephrotic syndrome	Nephritic syndrome	ARF	CRF	ATI	CTI	Hemato-proteinuria	RPRF	Other clinical features	Total
Focal segmental glomerulosclerosis	7	-	1	1	1	1	1	-	Lymphoma(1)	13
Membranous nephropathy	5	-	1	2	1	-	1	-	-	10
Type I membranous proliferative glomerulonephritis	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
IgA nephropathy	-	2	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	7

Crescentic glomerulonephritis	-	-	1	2	1	-	-	-	-	4
Diffuse proliferative glomerulonephritis	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Chronic glomerulosclerosis	1	-	3	4	-	-	1	-	-	9
Mesangio proliferative glomerulonephritis	1	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	4
Primary podocytopathy	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7
Lupus nephritis	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	2 (SLE)	6
Amyloidosis	2	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
Diabetic nephropathy	6	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
Acute tubulointerstitial nephritis	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
Acute tubular injury	1	1	9	-	-	-	-	-	HTN (2) DM (1) SNA (1)	15
Monoclonal immune deposition disease	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	HTN (1)	1
Kappa restricted light chain deposition disease	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
	32	3	24	9	4	1	14	1	8	96

Table 4: Frequency of immunoreactant positivity in renal diseases

Renal disease	IgG	IgM	IgA	Complement C3	C1Q	Kappa	Lambda
Focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (13)	-	-	4	-	-	4	4
Membranous nephropathy (10)	10	4	4	10	4	10	10
Type I membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis (1)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
IgA nephropathy (7)	2	-	7	7	-	7	7
Crescentic glomerulonephritis (4)	3	-	-	3	-	4	4
Diffuse proliferative glomerulonephritis (1)	1	-	-	1	-	1	1
Chronic glomerulosclerosis (9)	2	-	6	4	-	4	4
Mesangio proliferative glomerulonephritis (4)	1	1	4	4	1	3	3
Primary podocytopathy (7)	1	-	-	1	-	1	1
Lupus nephritis (6)	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Amyloidosis (4)	1	-	1	-	-	4	2
Diabetic nephropathy (10)	10	2	2	-	-	8	8
Acute tubulointerstitial nephritis (3)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Acute tubular injury (15)	2	-	5	1	1	6	6
Monoclonal immune deposition disease (1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Kappa restricted light chain deposition disease (1)	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
Total (96)							

DIRECT IMMUNOFLOUROSCENCE STAINING IN VARIOUS PATTERNS

Figure 1: Direct immunofluorescence staining in various patterns

Figure 2: Grading of direct immunofluorescence staining

Discussion

DIF continues to be an essential tool in diagnosing glomerular diseases, providing crucial insights into the presence and distribution of immunoreactants. Our study's findings of a high prevalence of primary glomerulonephritis (GN), particularly focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS) and membranous nephropathy, are consistent with recent studies by Minz RW, Chhabra S, Joshi K (2015), which identified these conditions as

predominant causes of nephrotic syndrome. In particular, our observation that 30.7% of FSGS cases exhibited IgA as the sole immunoreactant. Nephrotic syndrome was the most frequent clinical presentation across all age groups, accounting for 1/3rd (33.33%) of all cases.

This aligns with numerous other studies published globally, including those from Asiatic countries. Overall, a female predominance was observed. This observation slightly deviates from previous studies

worldwide. Our study's findings of uniform IgG, C3, kappa, and lambda light chain positivity in membranous nephropathy cases align closely with the recent work of William G. Couser (2005), who reported similar immunofluorescence patterns in patients with membranous nephropathy. This consistency across studies highlights the robustness of DIF as a diagnostic modality.

The identification of IgA nephropathy in 7.3% of our cases, characterized by mesangial IgA deposits along with strong correlation between DIF findings and clinical presentations, such as hemato-proteinuria, supports the diagnostic value of DIF in IgA nephropathy, as also demonstrated by Coppo et al. (2005).

Our study reinforces the importance of DIF in confirming IgA nephropathy, particularly in populations where this disease is prevalent. Our identification of diabetic nephropathy as the most common secondary glomerulonephritis aligns with recent global trends reported by Tervaert et al. (2010). The rare cases of monoclonal immune deposition disease and kappa-restricted light chain deposition disease showing bright staining of lambda and kappa chains observed in our study aligns with their findings, reinforcing the importance of DIF in diagnosing these rare renal pathologies and influencing treatment decisions.

In cases where light microscopy was inconclusive, The DIF can reveal immunoreactant deposits missed by light microscopy, leading to more accurate diagnoses and better patient outcomes. The complementary role of DIF in renal biopsy evaluation, as highlighted in both our study and recent literature, underscores its importance in the comprehensive assessment of renal pathologies. The identification of specific immunofluorescence patterns associated with different renal diseases can guide targeted therapy, improve prognostication, enhance patient care and potentially reduce the need for repeat biopsies.

Conclusion

Our study reaffirms the critical role of direct immunofluorescence in the diagnostic workup of renal biopsies. The consistency of our findings with recent studies further validates the use of DIF as a

standard diagnostic tool. The additional insights provided by DIF, particularly in complex or atypical cases, underscore its value in improving diagnostic accuracy and guiding clinical management.

Future studies, particularly those with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods, are needed to further explore the prognostic significance of DIF findings in various renal pathologies and to refine diagnostic criteria for rare and complex renal diseases.

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